

Response ID ANON-CX8K-BA14-6

Submitted to Developing UKRI's research data policy
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Introduction

1 Please provide your full name (title, first name and surname):

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2 Please provide your email address:

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3 Do you consent to UKRI contacting you about your response?

Yes, I consent to UKRI contacting me about my response

4 Do you consent to UKRI contacting you with updates about the development of the policy?

Yes, I consent to UKRI contacting me with updates about the development of the policy

5 Please indicate who you are responding on behalf of:

An organisation (including part of an organisation, department, informal group)

6 If you are responding on behalf of an organisation, please provide the name of the organisation (and specific part, if applicable):

If you are responding on behalf of an organisation, please provide the name of the organisation (and specific part, if applicable):
This response is submitted on behalf of The Turing Way Community, as endorsed by their Steering Committee, & On behalf of the Human Developmental Biology Initiative research consortium.

7 Please select the option that best describes the the capacity in which you, your organisation or your group are responding:

Other

If other, please specify:

This response is submitted with input from a variety of groups including Researcher(s), Providers of research data infrastructure or services, Library or research management, & Members of the Public

8 Please specify which country you, your organisation or your group are based in:

Please specify which country you, your organisation or your group are based in::
United Kingdom

9 Which disciplinary area(s) would you associate you, your organisation or your group with? Please select all that apply.

Medicine, health and life sciences

Feedback

10 Feedback regarding 'What this policy covers', 'Definitions' and 'Annex 1: supplementary information on policy scope'

Feedback regarding 'What this policy covers', 'Definitions' and 'Annex 1: supplementary information on policy scope':

- * The current framing of policy scope gives insufficient consideration to best practices for data generation & provenance. More weight & consideration should be given paradata about the objects that are in scope, meaning the processes by which they are generated. Whilst a workflow & the data that it produces are separate research outputs, the former is required for the latter to be optimally FAIR, & that dependency relationship is not adequately captured in the current framing.
- * Addressing these issues at the point of data generation also has significant potential for introducing much more robust systems for data provenance. These could contribute significantly to mitigating research integrity concerns associated with data tampering by increasing the analogue of 'supply chain security'. In short affirm the importance of paradata for data integrity & re-usability.
- * Additional Items which should be included as "research relevant digital objects"
- * Hardware designs as noted in the UNESCO Recommendations on Open Science (following established practice e.g. DIN SPEC 3105 <https://openhardware.science/2020/08/27/din-spec-3105-explained/> or the Open Know-How specification <https://standards.internetofproduction.org/pub/okh/release/>)
- * There is a strong trend towards open DIY hardware use in research. This is due to the greatly increased accessibility of low-cost low-volume custom

fabrication, & the ability iterate rapidly & with high degree of control over the manufacturing process that this affords. (See: Open hardware: From DIY trend to global transformation in access to laboratory equipment <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3001931>)

* Consequently the availability of, instructions, design files, & embedded software for open hardware are data which should be considered as in scope for the purpose of this policy. When such hardware is used to generate data this information makes up a part of the provenance information / paradata for the resulting data & making it available contributes to making the data FAIR.

* Services based on open hardware systems are also a significant & undervalued commercialisation opportunity. One without some of the tensions that business models based on closed & proprietary IP can generate with open science best practices. There is also a niche of hardware which is to specialised, low volume, & rapidly evolving to be commercially viable but is nonetheless highly valuable for increasing efficiency in particular research activities.

* Another consideration is that open hardware expands access to new technologies in low resource settings from international research environments with less funding, to schools for educational use where the ability to construct & understand the hardware is of added educational value & where commercial solutions may not make financial sense.

* Educational & Engagement materials: These are important research outputs for areas as diverse as the ability of other researchers to understand & apply newly developed methods to public engagement & understanding. These are also potentially important resources & source materials for social science researchers studying science & society.

* Greater Clarity about what objects are in scope & what constitutes a 'digital object'

* What about not 'natively' digital data should it be digitised?, under what circumstances?, & how are the costs of this to be covered?

* This question can arise in a wide range of scenarios, from whether or not to video an event or exhibition, to whether or not to digitise blots in biological experiments some of which are still produced on film.

* Examples of in & out of scope objects would be useful.

* Suggested Additional Definitions:

* Paradata: data on the making & processing of data (See: Perspectives on paradata: research & practice of documenting process knowledge <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-53946-6>)

* Software Management Plan (SMP): A Software Management Plan (SMP) details how a software project is developed, maintained, & curated, ensuring long-term accessibility & usability.

* As with data management plans promoting the use of software management plans can encourage, support & promote recognition of software as a research output & good practices in research software development such as FAIR principles for research software (FAIR4RS). As well as support & upskill researchers to develop higher-quality software, which is an increasingly important part of a researcher's professional portfolio.

11 Feedback regarding 'Key principles'

Feedback regarding 'key principles':

Missing principle: Integrous data generation & provenance

* A principle is needed which addresses generating data in appropriate formats & in transparent & reproducible ways, not merely sharing it in such. The brief allusion to generating data in open formats in the implementing FAIR data section is insufficient. Paradata: Data generation, provenance, integrity, and processes are incompletely addressed by the FAIR principles & need their own principle

Making data FAIR

* In implementing FAIR data it is insufficient to state "accepted domain-specific standards, formats & practices". There needs to be a push for open standards where accepted ones are closed, proprietary, or otherwise inadequate, but used due to lack of alternatives & collective action issues around addressing network effects which keep them in use. It must be clear to domains where closed standards are accepted that this will need to change

Appropriately preserving & retaining data

* To have a general framework & set of principles for developing domain specific preservation & retention policies & practices

* Clear lines of responsibility are needed for archiving. Valuable data must not be allowed to be lost, in the current model when funding for the project which generated the data ends it can be lost or cease to be generally available

* There should be clear criteria for a data repositories to meet for it to qualify as suitable for data generated with UKRI funds

* Central infrastructure should be provided for storage when no qualifying repository exists for the data in question so that retention obligations can be met

* Whilst each domain has its own unique data management needs wherever possible common tools & standards across domains should be pursued. This can facilitate interdisciplinary work, and reduce duplicative work in multiple disciplines

Acknowledging & recognising contributions

* Whenever possible authors should also be identified with a unique, persistent, resolvable Identifier such as an ORCID, & their affiliations with an ROR id

* Contributions should also be acknowledged with a contributor roles ontology or taxonomy (CROT) such as CRediT

* Contributorship & guarantorship models, instead to the authorship model should be used whenever appropriate

* crucial for understanding the knowledge production 'supply chain'

Planning for data sharing & management

* Data management plans should be machine readable/actionable whenever possible. Organisations requiring them should provide templates in such a machine readable/actionable format, to facilitate automations based upon DMPs & updates to them, to increase usability/utility & reduce administrative overhead

Resourcing data management & sharing

* An expansive view of what can be resourced here should be articulated, under-investment in the tooling & infrastructure necessary to facilitate effective & low friction research data management & sharing is a major barrier to adoption of best practices. Investment is necessary to make following best practices the default & least friction option instead of requiring considerable, sometimes immense effort to meet

* Include upstream contribution to existing open infrastructure upon which this function depends. For example contributions to open source resources depended on for good data management

* Funding for Research Technical Professionals from data curation, QC, & annotation to systems administration working on secure & performant access to shared research data resources

* Funding needs to be able to cover ongoing maintenance of important infrastructural projects not just new development

* The inverse is also true it is inappropriate for public money to fund data which is not to the public good. Public money should give rise to public code,

public data, & public papers. The benefits of IP created with public money should accrue to the public or public institutions & be accessible by the public, barring specific privacy & security concerns.

12 Feedback regarding 'Planning research' and any considerations you think UKRI should take into account in developing its approach and guidance for data management plans (DMPs) and support for costs.

Feedback regarding 'planning research' and any considerations you think UKRI should take into account in developing its approach and guidance for DMPs and support for costs.:

- * Making DMPs appropriate to project scope with minimal admin overhead
- * DMPs should be appropriate to the scope of the project. Guidance & templates for DMPs appropriate to different project's scopes would be aided by to standardised format for these DMPs & providing guidance on processes for developing new ones.
- * DMPs should be machine actionable, this can be achieved through the use of tools such as the Data Stewardship Wizard. DSW is an open source tool that has been adopted by other institutions, funders, & consortia for this purpose. This makes the automation of collection, aggregation, analysis & response to changes in the status of DMPs much easier.
- * Software management plans (SMP)
- * SMPs should be included in addition to DMPs. See section 10 for the suggested definition of a software management plan & see the software sustainability institute (SSI)'s checklist for an SMP: <https://zenodo.org/record/2159713>. Software is an increasingly common research output. Software is also a research output the quality of which can be disproportionately consequential. The same core software tools are frequently used to analyse numerous datasets so errors, quality & maintenance issues in research software can be of high impact.
- * The high degree of interest in the SSI's first research software maintenance fund grant scheme: <https://www.software.ac.uk/news/research-software-maintenance-fund-expressions-interest-outcomes-and-next-steps> is indicative of a need for funding.
- * As with DMPs scope should match that of the project.
- * Support for costs
- * Dedicated funding for planning
- * Proper data management planning needs to be situated in the larger context, this way the amount & type of data can be properly anticipated & detailed para/metadata can me provided about choices that were made when choosing what data to collect/generate & why.
- * Funding approaches which Incentivise good research planning practices, can be expected to bring down overall costs & increase research quality.
- * In particular a model with lends itself to this is registered reports (<https://www.cos.io/initiatives/registered-reports>). (see any other comments section)
- * Funding & Recognition for Research Technical Professionals
- * Many data management tasks require both the domain expertise of the researcher and the technical expertise of the of an RTP. Any given project may not have the need for a full-time RTP. Funding needs to be available both to core RTP teams & for researchers to make use of the services provided by them.
- * Funding for upstream enablers
- * Good data management depends on a number of important tools & resources which must themselves be developed, & maintained:
- * Ontologies & the tools for using & editing them
- * Ontologies, taxonomies, & Controlled vocabularies are essential for high quality interoperable metadata so that people can refer to the same phenomenon by the same name.
- * Actively maintained ontologies so when you discover something, such as a new cell type you can get it added to the ontology
- * For example tooling that make is easy to point to an ontology & generate a UI element for selecting things from that ontology when entering data.
- * Formats & Standards
- * An example of the value of work on file formats is the success of the sequencing data formats such as fastq & BAM which have enabled the vibrant genomics scene. Other data types have have comparatively impoverished ecosystems of tools. Current work on next generation file formats for image data are already having significant impact & similar efforts are needed in other domains e.g. proteomics.
- * Data Management Software
- * Software specialised for the collaborative management, curation, processing, & annotation data of a given type can be invaluable for increasing the efficiency of work with that data type at all stages from generation to sharing, e.g. OMERO for image data.
- * Funding these enablers avoids wasting effort on duplicative work, in addition to core funding, funding positions to add specific functionality needed for a project into existing upstream projects should be considered as part of other grants. Reseachers are often unable to adopt upstream tools a they do not meet their needs & upstream project lack the resources to add these features, addressing the problem upstream solves it for everyone.
- * Data reuse
- * Adopt policy which incentivises data reuse, or at minimum mitigates the "not invented here" problem where researchers feel obligated to produce novel data rather than use existing datasets.
- * Approaches to funding which explicitly encourage finding, curating, & even improving the annotations of existing datasets should be adopted. Researchers should be encouraged to budget for the time & resources spent on this.
- * Low discoverability of existing data due to poor quality & non-standardised metadata exacerbates this problem as it introduces risk & uncertainty into using existing data, resources must be invested into locating & quality controlling potential datasets. Better data reuse is dependent on better data annotation in the first place.
- * Encourage data citation over including identifiers in acknowledgments or data availability statements to ensure recognition of the value of the data reused is recognised in bibliometrics.
- * Long term commitments are needed to address these core information infrastructure systems.
- * Core funding needs to be sufficient for RTPs to keep on top of technical debt & with capacity to take on new additions to meet the needs of specific projects.
- * Large data management, & infrastructure development projects should be treated like many of the projects under STFC's umbrella.
- * Resources for controlled access repositories & trusted Research environments, see response to what data to share.

13 Feedback regarding 'What data to share'

Feedback regarding 'what data to share':

- * This is the WHAT data to share section but it is indicated that sharing should take place in a 'timely' fashion, this should probably be removed as there is a dedicated section on WHEN to share data & including it here just gives the impression that 'when' is left vague. A cross reference should be made to the 'When to share data' section if this is mentioned. The vagueness of 'timely' also undermines the statement in 'when to share data' that "Data necessary to understand and validate published findings (or other types of research output) must be shared no later than the time of publication."
- * The language around the criteria for data to be considered shared is slightly ambiguous. "To support data to be FAIR, they must be shared" implies that data must have these properties to be FAIR but not necessarily to be considered as shared under this policy. An alternative wording could be: "For data to be considered shared it must have the following minimum FAIR data properties:"

- * Terms such as "appropriate", "sufficient", & "adequate" are used without definition making this guidance far too vague to be practically useful!
- * What would make data appropriate/sufficient/adequate to share?
- * What criteria should be used to determine what data to share when developing a discipline specific specific fashion.
- * This policy should contain guidance/criteria for developing domain specific policies which can go into more detail as needed. Not every discipline has a well developed set of guidance for this.
- * Which pieces of intermediate data should be shared as opposed to the raw data & a description of the computations which can produce the secondary data.
- * How to identify major 'bookmark' points in analyses where it may be sensible to keep secondary data available.
- * compute / long term storage cost trade-off - imperfect computational reproducibility

14 Feedback regarding 'When to share data'

Feedback regarding 'when to share data':

- * There are a number of statements in this section with which to take issue.
- * A limited period of exclusive use of data collected & analysed is NOT necessarily reasonable in recognition of researchers' intellectual contribution.
- * Research teams should NOT necessarily have first opportunity to publish or otherwise exploit the data that they generate.
- * Longer periods of exclusive use CANNOT be justified in some of circumstances presented as validly permitting this.
- * Permitting PhD students to sit on their data until they have published/completed their PhD is teaching bad practice & should not be considered a valid reason for delaying data publication.
- * Large research collaborations & consortia have long precedent for agreeing to publish data upon generation, to suggest consortia may have grounds to delay release of data simply for being consortia would be a regression (see the Fort Lauderdale principles 2003).
- * Reasons for delaying data release should be specifically articulated & largely limited to:
 - * Privacy or other ethical concerns pertaining to data about humans
 - * Data quality concerns sufficiently severe to render it not worth archiving
 - * Where a patent is being sought
- * The model of post-publication data sharing is not fit for purpose & is one that perpetuates important structural issues in the conduct of research. This policy should be discourage this bad practice & encourage better alternatives.
- * Not publishing data as it is generated creates increased risk of / opportunities for the file-drawer effect, HARKing, p-hacking, & data falsification.
- * It is also disadvantages early career researchers & research technical professionals. In complex modern research projects where the expertise of multiple specialists is increasingly necessary to most research.
- * If high quality datasets suitable for posing important research questions are valued research outputs on their own this allows for appropriate credit & career progression opportunities for those who specialise in their generation.
- * It is common for a researcher who generated the data to have left by the time a paper is published. Important para/metadata can be lost in this time. Formalising para/metadata for deposition should be performed as early as possible to avoid this. Researchers can then get credit for the data they have generated immediately.
- * Review of data/methods publications can be performed by appropriate specialists, & in a timely fashion instead of potentially years after its initial generation/development.
- * A suitable mechanism for claiming precedence is a pre-registration or registered report, see other comments.
- * Exclusive use of data means that it is not published in a timely fashion. As soon as a dataset exists analysts may benefit from using it as a basis for decision making. In some contexts this can be highly time sensitive e.g. public health.
- * 'No later than the time of publication' is insufficient it should be BEFORE final publication, if papers are published before data is made available publishers lose significant leverage in enforcing their data sharing policies.
- * Without publication as a clear indicator of the latest point before which data should be made available, what points are appropriate junctures for data/methods sharing/publication?
- * When data is generated by or with the help of a technical specialist facility or third party service. This is a point at which data publication should be considered. If specialist informatics are needed to finish data QC after it is produced this should precede data sharing to avoid archiving data of insufficient quality.
- * After data pertaining to any pre-registered hypothesis is generated but before/as it is analysed as planned.
- * When developing methods the protocol for their use should be published at minimum once revisions based on pilot scale data are complete, any revisions based on full scale datasets should follow in an update to the protocol.

15 Feedback regarding 'Where to share data'

Feedback regarding 'where to share data':

- * Criteria for the Suitability of repositories for storing UKRI funded data
- * By what criteria is a repository to be judged as a suitable place to share data?
- * What data retention, & preservation practices do they need to adhere to?
- * What metadata standards do they need to adhere to?
- * Central guidance on these points would be welcome, what should be the default in the absence of existing well developed domain specific norms?

* There are a plethora of different domain & data type specific repositories. They use different tooling, metadata representations etc. This results in a lot of duplicative work & incompatibilities. Central impetus to adopt metadata schemas with structures which can be validated against a schema & which make use ontologies, taxonomies, &/or controlled ontologies, & which can readily be converted to RDF triple representations should be pursued, possession of these features & enforcement of their use should be criteria for assessing if a repository is suitable to house data from UKRI projects.

* Sharing Software

* Wherever possible research software applications should be packaged for their language's own specific package format and distributed via any major repositories that is has &/or a functional package manager format & repository, due to their unique advantages for specifying computational environments in a reproducible fashion, for example Nix &/or Guix.

* To further this in the software context:

* Access to technical review of code is rarely a part of conventional peer review but is available through initiatives like rOpenSci, & PyOpenSci. There is also review specialised on research software portability / reproducibility such as CODECHECK & ReproHack.

* Provide means to financially support community software peer review efforts: Such as opportunities to fund infrastructure such as code hosting with compute resources for CI/CD; Training in these activities to expand the pool of reviewers; Support for technical review activity in the roles of research technical professionals who might not be engaged with these review processes due to lower exposure to conventional peer review.

* Repositories with review, curation, & annotation services which add value to data should be prioritised.

* It is essential high quality standards in annotation & metadata are maintained by data repositories as resources can be wasted storing data rendered useless by lack of the contextual information necessary to reuse it. This requires proper staffing & training for RTPs with expertise in data stewardship & information management at these data repositories.

* The value of, quality control, review of metadata & annotation for consistency, completeness, & conformance to metadata schemas; as well as assistance to 'uplift' data lacking optimal annotations in collaboration with the data submitter, is difficult to understate for its impact on the quality of deposited records.

* Both staff to perform this function & resources to develop improved software for data submission portals to increase efficiency of operations for both submitters & curators are needed.

* Choosing data storage technologies with strategic resilience

* Adopt underlying storage technologies which facilitate easy mirroring of research data by arbitrary third parties as well as in centrally managed repositories & which can allow peer-to-peer sharing of this data, as well as names which resolve independently of where the data is hosted. This could massively ease preservation efforts which can mitigate losses if any given repository of data suffers some form of catastrophe.

16 Feedback regarding 'Implementing FAIR data'

Feedback regarding 'implementing FAIR data':

* Licences for data reuse

* For improved machine actionability of complex & multi-license projects recommend the use of SPDX <https://spdx.org/licenses/> license codes in file headers & REUSE <https://reuse.software/> to automate this.

* Copyleft / share-alike clauses which can help to ensure the continued openness of derived works should be explicitly permitted as these can be construed as restrictions on use.

* Data formats

* "UKRI recognises that for some research use of a proprietary format may be preferable" it should be made clear that this state of affairs is one that needs to be moved away from by adding some qualifiers to the language used here: "use of a proprietary format may be at present in practice preferable". It should also be indicated that efforts to move away from proprietary formats are desirable & will be supported, including financially. It should be clear that proprietary formats should be phased out whenever & wherever it is possible to do so.

* It should be more specific that proprietary formats should not be used for new data generation where control of the format is possible, unless the purpose is to study the format itself. Proprietary formats should not be considered suitable for data preservation unless archiving an existing large dataset in a proprietary forms where no means currently exists to preserve it in an open format.

* Data in proprietary formats should be collected for limited purposes such study of the format itself, e.g. studying the format to allow reverse engineering to permit conversion to open formats, studying the implication of the design of the format for security, privacy, & functionality for users.

* Data access statement

* Make it clear the "available upon request from the authors is inadequate"

* Full details of any access criteria or requirements must be provided where they are imposed

* Resources must be provided to store & if necessary appropriately manage access to data so researchers do not feel unable to find a suitable place to deposit some data types.

* Guidance needs to be available on writing consent documents in such a fashion as to be compatible with placing data in appropriate 3rd party repositories.

17 Feedback about 'Acknowledgement and recognition' and 'Citing and reusing data'

Feedback about 'acknowledgement and recognition' and 'citing and reusing data':

* CRediT is cited as an example of a contributor roles ontology or taxonomy (CROT) but it lacks applicability to all fields, does not include some forms of contribution, has quite ambiguously defined roles, & lacks granularity.

* For a review on the ethics of CROT's see: DOI: 10.1080/08989621.2022.2161049

* Good to see the recommendation of ORCIDs & RORs

* Advise that citation of data, protocols, & code should be excluded from caps on the number of references imposed by journals.

* There is ambiguity around what constitutes 'appropriately' citing data sources.

* It is currently somewhat ambiguous when it is appropriate to cite papers vs. data generated alongside them directly by identifiers for the data.

* Encourage wider adoption of annotations to the edges in the citation graph, for example citations of data should include the "Uses Data From" term or other related & appropriate terms from the Citation Typing Ontology (CITO) in the reference where possible. This has immense value for future bibliometrics. Better support for annotated citations is an example of the potential value of investment in upstream tooling, adoption of citation annotations could be facilitated by adding features that support this in tools such as Zotero, BibTeX, Pandoc, MyST etc.

- * Current REF 2029 CKU guidance contains a commitment to recognise outputs & practice other than journal articles & includes output types that represent significant progress as well as aligning with this policy. However, this guidance contains a number of issues for properly giving credit to research data outputs & practices & should ideally be altered to improve compatibility with the goals of this policy.
- * REF 2029, erroneously, excludes contributions to standards development as research activity. Early & ongoing involvement of researchers developing new techniques in standards development is crucial to early & wide adoption of shared open standards & avoiding the inefficient & costly proliferation of proprietary 'standards'. The work of the scientific imaging community on developing next generation file format standards exemplifies this.
- * Whilst seeking to acknowledge 'diverse outputs' it remains focused on fixed point outputs, there is need to for appropriate credit for ongoing outputs.
- * For example there is need to explicitly include in software & code that this is not limited to new software packages & analysis code but includes maintenance, addition of new features to existing projects, & contributions to upstream dependencies, or downstream consumers of research code. Ensuring that it is understood that these are creditworthy activities is essential to reduce duplication of effort, as well as increasing the quality & longevity of research code.
- * The guidance is somewhat contradictory on proper credit for ongoing & infrastructural functions essential to research data management. In 5.3 research is defined to include "scholarship" defined as including development & maintenance of intellectual infrastructure, but in 6.3 discussing eligible employment relationships, role descriptors are required to include research activity as distinct from scholarship. It is unclear what this means but introduces ambiguity as to where these important activities are to be given appropriate credit.
- * Recognition of ongoing work in active maintenance & development of research enabling infrastructural resources such as research software, research data curation, annotation, & management, as well as contribution to the tools a projects upstream of these activities is important to them receiving proper funding. Many of these activities have the potential for massively multiplicative returns on research productivity but are under-resourced due to lack of recognition leaving them 1 or 2 steps removed from what is considered primary research activity despite being integral to this process.

18 Feedback about 'Data retention and preservation'

Feedback about 'data retention and preservation':

Lines of responsibility for data preservation are often unclear

- * Generic guidance for this question, or at least for how to approach answering this question, is needed for those where there is not a well developed domain specific framework
 - * Lack of clarity here leads to duplication & long retention of data which may not need to be retained, as well as the loss of data which should have been retained
 - * Who should be responsible for preserving what data?
 - * Should research institutions preserve data that is also deposited in public archival repositories? What criteria do repositories have to meet for researcher to meet their retention obligations if they use them?
 - * How should it be determined how long is appropriate?
 - * "domain specificity" of approaches can be in tension with interdisciplinary collaboration, & should be strictly as necessary with a push for standardisation in underlying tools with the flexibility to accommodate varied use cases wherever possible
- Articulate a more comprehensive strategic vision for long term research data storage technologies which can facilitate research data sharing, retention & preservation best practices
- * Consider the advantages available if research data infrastructure adopted a common underlying standard for identifying & distributing data with a feature set similar to that of the interplanetary file system (IPFS)
 - * Content Identifiers (CIDs)
 - * Globally unique persistent identifiers
 - * Resolvable independent of where they are physically hosted as long and anyone is still hosting them, providing resilience that is transparent to the end user
 - * CIDs provides a built-in check that the requested content is the content that was received when retrieving it from another source as the expected hash of the file is contained within the identifier.
 - * File format optimised chunks
 - * The way in which file are broken into chunks to be stored in a system like IPFS can be optimised for order in which it chunks might be requested & read e.g. a video stream or a sorted BAM file can use a 'trickle' rather than a 'balanced' approach to generating a merkle DAG when chunking the file.
 - * Reduced distribution costs
 - * Data can easily be distributed peer to peer between any research facilities which currently have a copy & allocate the upload bandwidth to allow the data egress.
 - * No need for central repositories to invest in expensive CDNs (content distribution networks) or as much of their own bandwidth.
 - * Reduced unintentional data duplication
 - * Identifiers generated for the same content, (*with the same data representation settings) produces the same ID. Thus if two people add the same data to the network in the same way no duplication occurs
 - * Simplified data deposition workflows for transferring files
 - * Simply adding files to a local node & supplying a list of IDs to a repository to pin so they can pull them from your node
 - * Disaster resilience & Censorship resistance
 - * This is a unified approach to data distribution suitable for large central entities & unofficial, distributed or volunteer groups. All a user has to do is pin the ID on their node so they will keep a local copy of it & have the ability to share it peer-to-peer with others
 - * Anyone who needs data to preserved beyond when it was originally expected to be deleted can pin it before it is removed from the network & continue to share it with the rest of the network to no change to consumers of the data
 - * Data citation information which uses CIDs from a system like this can readily be parsed to a list of the IDs of all the data used in a publication, as the IDs are all that is needed to retrieve the data this would make it trivial to automate retrieval of all data from potentially disparate sources
 - * This extends to things like retrieving software dependencies, There has already been some work incorporating these approaches into the build systems of functional package management tools

19 Feedback about 'Responsible data sharing'

Feedback about 'responsible data sharing':

- * With whom is it responsible to share what data?
- * Resources are needed for additional training for researchers in this area.
- * Ethics - Referencing Ethics Approvals
- * For all human participants research a persistent, resolvable, global identifier as a reference to the ethics approval is a critical piece of metadata.
- * Ethics approvals in the Health Research Authority's National Research Ethics Service (NRES) directory can be located by search using their IRAS ID, but the pages for individual application summaries cannot be referred to directly by a standard URL that varies only by this identifier.
- * For other Research Ethics Committees (RECs) not part of the NRES: Higher education institution (HEI) RECs & Ministry of Defence (MoDRECs), there is no central database. This means that it can be very difficult to locate & verify summaries of the ethics approvals carried out by these bodies using only the reference numbers usually used to reference them in the literature. This is a significant issue for the transparency of this process in practice.
- * Policy should be introduced to require that ethics approvals should be referred to using a persistent, resolvable, global identifier. Research ethics committees need to make their summaries available via an identifier with these characteristics & introducing such a requirement would ensure that they do so.
- * Funding should ideally be made available to construct & maintain a national database of research ethics applications to include all such applications, in the absence of such an effort RECs can avail themselves of one of the many existing tools, e.g. zenodo, to generate suitable identifiers for their summaries.
- * Patient information sheets which accompany consent forms are also important metadata & where ever possible to be included in information about ethics approvals.
- * Researchers assessing the appropriate & ethical re-use of a human dataset should have access to this information about the initial approval of the work to ensure that their re-use complies with the letter & spirit of conditions under-which participants consented to the data collection.
- * Controlled access repositories & Trusted Research Environments (TREs)
- * Controlled Access Repositories
- * Resources need to be made available to fund Data Access Committees to process access requests & assess the ability of applicants to meet the requirements for the stewardship of the data to which they are being granted access.
- * Mechanisms need to be create to appeal denials of access requests & measures taken to inquire equitable access to data gated in this fashion.
- * Training for researchers is needed on the appropriate use of controlled access repositories.
- * TREs
- * TREs should follow a strict policy of having a fully open source & portable technology stack which would allow their re-deployment on other compute infrastructure or their trustworthiness, integrity, security, & the reproducibility / validity of results arising from them cannot be fully validated by independent third parties who could otherwise provide a degree of assessment of the technical correctness of methods employed in such environments even without access to the data.

20 Any other feedback or comments

Any other feedback or comments:

- * compliance & monitoring
- * End of grant reporting & assessment needs to be well resourced to assess compliance with this policy & compliance should be actively investigated & recorded.
- * criteria supplied above should allow for the administrability of end of grant assessment. If they are to vague compliance cannot easily be assessed & thus cannot effectively inform future funding decisions
- * Compliance with the standards for data sharing set out in this policy should be consider the minimum requirements for the professional conduct of modern research.
- * Support to meet the obligations of this policy is essential but there need to be negative consequences for future funding applications for poor compliance as there are perverse incentives which reward failure to comply with some aspects of this policy. Thus In the absence of a cost associated with non-compliance, which exceeds this, merely providing support for compliance is inadequate to achieve it.
- * Grant application documentation should indicate that less than optimal compliance with research data polices of previous grants will count against those applying for new funding.
- * Applicants with a track record of good open data practices should be favoured over those with records of less transparent data practices.
- * For first / early career applications lack a track record should not count against them.
- * Applications which include robust data management & open practices planning should be favoured over those which do not.
- * Applications with robust open data planning which also originate from a group with strong open science record should be favoured over either of these criteria alone.
- * A track record of not performing suitable data sharing should count against subsequent applications.
- * If previous grant applications include explicit commitments to conform to open data policies which have not been fulfilled this should count against the applicant.
- * For research quality standards to be upheld compliance with these policies should be an overriding consideration in funding decisions. It does not matter how interesting the scientific question a grant addresses if the results of that research are inadequately recorded allowing for the proper assessment of it's quality & validity through critical examination of its methods & conclusions in future work.
- * The development effort necessary to produce tooling for this kind of system is considerable but has the potential for massive long term benefits.
- * What about when current domain specific norms are not good practice and should be changed? - Where domain specific norms & established practices are sub-optimal with respect to FAIR principles their reform should be pursued. Consensus in favour of reform should be sought, but funding leveraged to incentivise transition away from entrenched bad practices.
- * More on the potential role of registered reports in research planning
- * In this model you introduce & plan your experiment(s) & methods, publish this plan, have the plan reviewed & refined. If a publication accepts a plan they commit to publishing the results, if the plan was followed. Allowing authors to establish precedence in a way which does not incentivise rushing to a result. A prominent publication venue for the results can therefore be secured before the data is generated.
- * An interesting approach is to couple funding to this workflow, e.g. funding the first planning part of the project & only funding the planned experiment contingent on the publication of the plan. The resources necessary to perform this level of planning are high, separating funding for this ensures researchers can feel comfortable to front-load large portions of the work which would typically be done later in a project.

* Many publication venues now support registered reports, funding models which complement this may now be a larger barrier to adoption than limitations on publication venue.